

NUMERICAL ASSESSMENT OF CAPILLARY PRESSURE BY FLOW SIMULATION IN A FIBROUS MEDIUM

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ABSTRACT

Abstract

The aim of the present work, which lies at the heart of the Hexcel-Mines Saint-Etienne Industrial Chair [1, 2, 3], is to set up numerical modeling tools applicable from the component scale (local or microscopic scale) to the process scale (macroscopic scale), based on fluid-solid coupling methods undergoing finite strains within a high performing computing framework. At the local scale, the aim is to model flows in the fibrous network of preforms where wettability and capillary effects are assumed to play a key role [4]. First, at the fibre scale, the resin flow in impervious fibre systems will be characterized and modeled. Then, flows inside and around fibre tows, will be studied relying on some specific stabilized [5] and enriched [6] numerical methods able to deal with coupled Stokes-Darcy flows in low permeability orthotropic media.

Capillary and viscous dominated flows competing at the local scale will be used to provide, at the meso/macroscopic scale, equivalent capillary pressures representing these local phenomena. Capillary effects will be included in numerical simulations of local flows in industrial parts with complex geometries. The ultimate goal of this approach is to yield a robust numerical modeling of infusion processes at the scale of industrial parts in order to understand and hence control both filling and post-filling stages for industrial applications.

1. Introduction

Primary composite structures in aeronautics have to meet quality requirements (i.e. 1% max void content) which can only be achieved by using costly and time-consuming means of production. The aeronautics industry aim is to product three times more single-aisle aircraft per month by 2020 with the same quality, both at reduced costs and for increasingly complex structures. "Out-of-autoclave" processes (i.e. Liquid Resin Infusion processes) are the most promising routes. However, controlling those processes is still a challenge and the use of numerical modelling currently appears to be one of the main areas of development in understanding the mechanical (solid, fluid, porous) and thermo-physico-chemical phenomena occurring simultaneously during the process. For the last past years a numerical framework has been developed at Mines Saint-Etienne to model these processes, along with dedicated experimental means to follow the major driving mechanisms. The Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) process consists in impregnating fibrous reinforcements with a liquid resin flowing in the thickness direction, by pulling vacuum out of the system. Thus, at macroscopic scale, the resin flow is mainly driven by the pressure gradient generated by vacuum assistance. However, it has been experimentally demonstrated that capillary effects resulting from carbon reinforcements and epoxy resin or water interaction at a lower scale, can reach a value of 0.3-0.4bar [7,8] which represents a third of the process driving force. Consequently, the aim of this paper is to establish a 3D numerical model that takes into account these capillary effects in the macroscopic simulation of orthotropic composite material manufacturing processes such as LRI process [3].

2. Mathematical and numerical settings

At macroscopic scale, the resin flow through fibrous reinforcements is assumed to be described by Darcy's equation, which relates the flow velocity to the pressure gradient and three parameters: the fluid viscosity, the preform permeability and its porosity. The fibrous reinforcement high orthotropy results in an orthotropy of both the permeability and the capillary effects (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Illustration of wicking in the 3 main directions of a fabric [7].

2.1. At meso-scale

The model is implemented in a mixed finite element framework with a continuous piecewise linear approximation for the velocity and pressure variables. A variational multiscale method [5] ensures the numerical consistency of the fluid problem. Capillary pressure is applied at the flow front described by a level set function, as a natural interface condition of the Darcy's problem ruling flow in preforms. This strategy generates a pressure discontinuity at the flow front. Moreover, spurious velocities appear around the fluid interface because the standard pressure space does not allow a sharp variation of the variable. In order to circumvent those oscillations, a local pressure enrichment [1] is used. This consists in adding pressure degrees of freedom with discontinuous shape functions in the elements crossed by the interface. Note that this technique does not increase the size of the algebraic system, since these new degrees of freedom can be condensed prior to the global assembly. Thereafter, the model is validated with the method of manufactured solution [9] in order to calculate the convergence rates. Good convergence rates are obtained for both velocity and pressure fields.

2.2. At micro-scale

Capillary effects that occur at the interface between three phases (liquid, gas, solid) are conditioning the quality of an interface that is a key parameter in composite materials. Those effects have been experimentally quantified and included in a finite element framework at the

scale of an industrial part [7;9]. At a lower scale, an enforcement of the triple junction at the interface of the three phases, namely fluid solid and vapour, has been implemented in a finite element software, allowing to weakly impose the force equilibrium [10-11]. This enforcement has been validated by comparison with experimental data [12-13] and is now used to simulate wicking to evaluate an equivalent capillary pressure in a porous medium.

2 Theory

The finite elements mathematical setting with a linear approximation is suited to describe a bi-fluid problem where the liquid represents the resin and the vapour phase represents the air. Solving the Stokes equation using mixed velocity-pressure simplices stabilised with an Algebraic SubScale method [5] yields the velocity and the pressure fields in the domain (fluid and vapour). The interface between the liquid and the vapour is followed and captured with a levelset method, convected with the flow velocity.

Pressure jump and gradient pressure jump arise from the sudden change in physical properties such as density and viscosity across the interface. Therefore an enrichment of the pressure space is mandatory to capture physics of a bi-fluid problem since linear approximation is not rich enough. Three degrees of freedom with discontinuous and gradient discontinuous shape functions are added in the elements cut by the interface [6]. The asset of the extended finite element method used in this method is that the size of the system remains unchanged since the three added degrees of freedom are condensed prior to assembly.

As depicted in fig.1, there are three interfaces to be considered, first between the fibres and the resin, second between the fibres and the air, and third between the resin and the air. At each interface the jump of the normal stress gives rise to a capillary force substituted into the weak form of the Stokes equations as a Neumann condition. Modifications for each surface tension force, using the Laplace-Beltrami operator [11] yield a new expression allowing to include the mechanical equilibrium of the triple line into the weak formulation. Subsequently, the contact angle is enforced as a natural condition, without explicitly considering the contact angle of the liquid over the solid phase, unlike classical methods [13].

Fig.2 Domain for calculation and interfaces definition

The domain for calculation will be referred to as Ω , here in a 2D space, describing a fibrous microstructure in which a newtonian fluid flows. Fibres are considered as rigid and non-deformable and are represented as holes in Ω (Fig. 1). The domain contains both liquid and gas phases referred respectively to as Ω_l and Ω_g implying that $\Omega = \Omega_l \cup \Omega_g$. The liquid-gas interface is referred to as Γ_{lg} . Γ_{ls} et Γ_{gs} are respectively the liquid-solid and gas-solid interfaces. Triple lines are defined as the intersections of those 3 interfaces (point P in Fig.1 in 2D). This 2D description can be extended in 3D as Bruchon *et al* [3] have demonstrated it.

Interfaces Γ_{lg} , Γ_{ls} and Γ_{gs} are holding surface tension γ_{lg} and surface energies γ_{ls} and γ_{gs} resulting from unbalanced potentials on each side of the interface. In the 2D case from Fig.1, at point P, the force equilibrium writes:

$$\gamma_{lg} \mathbf{t}_{lg} + \gamma_{ls} \mathbf{t}_{ls} + \gamma_{gs} \mathbf{t}_{gs} = -\mathbf{R}_s \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{R}_s is the solid reaction, that is not considered here since the solid is considered as rigid and non-deformable. Nevertheless, it would have a significant effect if we consider elastocapillarity.

The last point of the method deals with the coupling strategy between both the levelset and Stokes problem. As in any bi-fluid problem, the equations describing the flow depend, in a non-linearly way, on the interface position, and therefore on the level-set function [12-13]. A staggered coupling between Stokes and levelset method is used in this paper. During a time increment, one Stokes problem with capillarity action and one levelset problem are solved. Considering several fibres with an arrangement allowing capillary wicking, we should be able to identify the cosine of the apparent advancing contact angle $\cos\theta_a$ from the Washburn equation describing the mass of a liquid wicking in a porous cylindrical medium:

$$m^2(t) = \left[\frac{(c\bar{r})\epsilon^2(\pi R^2)^2}{2} \right] \frac{\rho^2 \gamma_L \cos\theta_a}{\eta} t \quad (2)$$

where R is the radius of the cylindrical sample holder, η the viscosity of the liquid and ρ its density, ϵ the porosity of the fibrous medium, c is a parameter related to tortuosity and r the mean capillary radius in the porous medium described by the Washburn law and t the time of flow. The squared mass gain, and thus the squared height of the flow front, should thus be linear as a square root of time.

3. Results and validations

2.2. At micro-scale

Simulations carried out at the fibre scale are conducted to compute and verify, values of capillary pressures. The parameters that have been entered in the model are described in Tables 2 and 3. The idealized arrangements of fibers used in first approach, along with boundary conditions are depicted in Fig. 3.

Table 2. Surface tension values [7]

	Solid/Vapour	Solid/Liquid	Liquid/Vapour
Surface tension (10^3 N/m)	60.9	30.0	72.8

Table 3. Fluids parameters [7]

	Vapour	Liquid
Viscosity (Pa.s ⁻¹)	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Density (kg.m ⁻³)	1.2	$1.0 \cdot 10^3$

Figure 3. Wicking simulation in a perfect hexagonal arrangement of fibers.

Figure 4. Kinetics of numerical wicking in an hexagonal arrangement.

Fig. 4 shows the kinetics of wicking resulting from the simulation. The main results that can be drawn from this figure is that the trend is linear considering the height of the flow front against the square root of time. This confirms that the method used for simulating the wetting

is able to describe wicking in a fibrous medium. The slope of the curves also allows the calculation of a numerical capillary pressure, which is a main result.

The same steps have been used in order to evaluate the capillary pressure on a random repartition of fibres. A software to generate statistically representative volumes have been used [14] and proper hypotheses have been made to be as close as possible to a unidirectional flow. The domain used for simulation is described in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Scheme of the domain for numerical capillary pressure calculation

As can be seen on Fig.6, it is possible to validate a Washburn law with those hypotheses: the squared height of the flow front is linear against time. It is important to note here that it is not a regular spontaneous Washburn case since a complementary pressure must be prescribed at this fibre volume fraction.

Figure 6. Verification of the flow front height change versus square root of time.

Thanks to some simulations based on Fig. 5, both in saturated flow to estimate the permeability of the medium and in unsaturated flow, it has been possible to compute a numerical capillary pressure. Fig. 7 shows that a calculation of capillary pressure (time permeability here, but the permeability is assumed to be constant for capillary pressure calculation) at each time of wicking is possible. It quickly converges towards a constant value that allows to provide quantitative results.

Figure 7. Calculation and stabilization of the capillary pressure

From this study, permeability values have been estimated between $2.3 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2$ and $5.5 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2$ (depending on the calculation method) which allows estimating the capillary pressure between 0.18 and 0.42 bar. It sounds reasonable to conclude that capillary effects are significant during an unsaturated flow, since the pressure gradient during manufacturing is 1 bar, and have to be taken into account.

5. Conclusions

It has been demonstrated here that both wetting and capillary effects can be represented through capillary stresses, acting at the liquid/air interface. This stress can then be implemented in Darcy's equations as an input parameter. The numerical model gives the expected behavior for capillary wicking and shows a good correlation with experimental data, as well as with the analytical model of Washburn's equation. A better description of those capillary effects and a more accurate comparison between experimental data and numerical simulation is ongoing and will be the main topic of further works.

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